

Exploring the Growth and Future Potential of Orthodox Tea in Nepal: Cultivation, Promotion, and Future Prospects

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Abstract

Orthodox tea stands out as a valuable agricultural commodity with significant potential for export in the international market. Many parts of Nepal have a suitable climate, soil, and topography, which is well-positioned to achieve profitable production of orthodox tea, distinguished by its outstanding flavor, smell, and taste. Our research aimed to assess the production trends, annual growth rates, barriers of export dynamics, and the future projections of Nepali orthodox tea. A quantitative approach and a survey study were applied to understand the opinions, ideas, and experiences of the tea industrialists of Nepal. Our study applied the survey questionnaire to collect data from the two-hundred and ten (N= 210) industrialists who produce and export tea themselves. The issues of ethical concern of the respondents were considered following the human study's principle during the research processes.

The expected results would reveal a growing trend in tea production, averaging an annual growth rate of 12%. Despite substantial opportunities in both domestic and international markets, Nepal currently produces only a limited quantity of orthodox tea. The results would further show that there would be an increase of 90% in the production of orthodox tea, which can be imported, mainly to India, contributing to sub-optimal premiums compared to other tea-exporting nations like other SAARC countries.

It is suggested to concentrate on enhancing tea productivity through mechanization, establishing tea processing industries, implementing streamlined certification processes, intervening in pricing, gaining market recognition, and fostering diplomatic relations for improved market accessibility and duty-free trade to regenerate the tea sub-sector.

Keywords: *export dynamics, future potential, orthodox tea, Nepal, production trends*